

COMMON MISTAKES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: In today's rapidly developing globalization, the demand for young personnel who master foreign languages is increasing day by day. This is the reason for the increase of interest in foreign languages among young people and the wide popularity of learning foreign languages. In this article, we will consider some mistakes, problematic situations and their analysis that are made by young people who have just started learning foreign languages.

Key words: one-sided goal; fear of speaking; learning styles; to become attached to the teacher; language environment.

Of course, every person aims to achieve a certain goal by doing something. In addition, new language learners who have started to learn English, French, German or any other Eastern languages aim to achieve a certain goal and result by learning these languages. Unfortunately, some language learners make mistakes at this step and face a number of difficulties later in the language learning process.

The fact is that nowadays, most of the young people who learn foreign languages try to achieve a one-sided result by learning this language, that is, by learning a new foreign language, they only want to achieve good results in entrance tests, the language they are learning. they aim to obtain a language certificate or simply to develop conversational skills in this language. This causes the formation of a superficial attitude to the language being studied. Instead, such a superficial attitude towards the language they are learning prevents them from fully understanding the language, its unique expressions and complexities, and as a result, they will not be able to achieve the success they expected from learning this language. This has a negative effect on their desire to learn foreign languages, and they come to the conclusion that "this is not my mother tongue, I don't need to know this language completely." In fact, this view of the language learning process is completely wrong. Learning foreign languages and being able to speak fluently in the studied language requires a serious approach to learning this language. Only a serious, not superficial, approach to language learning will open the way to a full understanding of this language, its complexities, and to communicate in this language without difficulties in the future.

Another problem faced by young learners who have just started to learn Khori languages is their fear of making mistakes while learning and using this language. Of course, avoiding making mistakes in the process of language learning builds the ability of language learners to be responsible for the language, but this process slows down language learning and the learner gradually loses the ability to speak the language. may lead to difficulties in full development. Usually, a language learner tries to avoid making mistakes in grammatical rules during the conversation in the language he is learning, which causes him to get distracted and confuse the content of the thought being spoken. This leads to the listener not being able to fully understand the idea. It should not be forgotten that there are mistakes and shortcomings

in any newly started work, it is natural. Pronunciation disorders and grammatical errors in the speech of new language learners can be solved by constantly working on yourself and increasing the practice of speaking the given language.

Another mistake made by new language learners is that they become too dependent on the teacher's support and avoid working on themselves. Of course, it is optimal to rely on the teacher's explanations and help in the process of language learning, but it is a solution to minor complications related to language learning that occur in the process of independent work, when students avoid working on themselves or work less on themselves. Failure to find them will lead to slow learners' language learning skills and poor results. It should not be forgotten that foreign language skills cannot be built based on the speech of one person, because usually the speech of teachers in that foreign language is very different from the speech of indigenous people who speak that foreign language. One of the best ways to avoid such problems is to watch movies and listen to podcasts and radio broadcasts in that language. One of the problems faced by new foreign language learners is the overabundance of foreign language programs and the inability of young people to choose the most suitable training programs and then transfer them to training programs. is the inability to get away. Sometimes, which method is more effective in learning foreign languages? face-to-face with a teacher or in groups? This question arises in front of young people who have just started to learn the language.

Observations show that the above two methods of learning foreign languages have their own advantages and disadvantages. For example, by learning foreign languages in groups, it is possible to quickly develop the ability to speak a foreign language, and to strengthen the information learned in the lesson through mutual questions and answers. However, during the study of foreign languages in groups, it is also possible to face problems such as the time allotted is not enough to work with all the students, the information given in the lesson is not equally understandable to everyone [1, 2]. In the process of learning foreign languages alone with the teacher, the learner should have the opportunity to get answers to all the questions that arise in relation to the language, the subject should be relatively understandable and not be distracted by unnecessary things during the lesson. will have amenities. But learning a language prevents the development of speaking skills in this language. Regarding this problem, Tony Robbins states that "Even the best methods and rules are only 20 percent of success, and the remaining 80 percent depends on human psychology" [2, p. 73]. It should not be forgotten that the key to success is hard work and effort. One of the problematic situations that arise in the process of language learning is inability to adapt to a new language environment, difficulty in understanding that language. Usually such a problem is the absence of speakers of this language or those who know this language around the language learner. This problem can cause the language learner to quickly forget the newly learned words and information. An optimal way to solve this problem is to create the environment of the language being studied by the learner. In this regard, it is very useful for a language learner to first of all try to remember the names of the things he uses the most in daily life and, if possible, to write down the names of these things in the language he is learning. This method helps the names of objects in a foreign language to be easily learned and kept in memory for a long time. In addition, listening to music in a foreign language and observing the pronunciation of words while listening to music with the text of this music helps to develop listening and pronunciation skills more successfully.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order not to make mistakes and face problems in the process of learning foreign languages, it is necessary to be more responsible for language learning, to work on oneself regularly. Consistency is necessary to achieve success not only in language learning, but in any task. Only then can you achieve complete mastery of the language being studied.

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